

Control of helminthosporiose of rice. Rice Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India.

Treatment	Dose/ha	1977-78 seasons			
		Kharif		Rabi	
		Disease index (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Disease index (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Edifenphos	0.5 liter	53	1.9	57	1.3
Zineb	2.0 kg	49	2.0	53	1.4
Mancozeb	2.0 kg	54	1.9	56	1.4
Captafol	2.0 kg	55	1.8	59	1.3
Copper oxychloride	2.0 kg	53	1.8	58	1.3
Aureofungin sol	0.05 kg	56	1.9	58	1.3
IBP	1.0 liter	50	2.0	58	1.4
Control	-	59	1.7	67	1.2
CD (0.05)		n.s.	n.s.	6.71	0.114

Plants treated with mancozeb, edifenphos, and IBP were amply protected but did not give commensurate yield increases (see table). ■

Herbicides in plant disease control

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A field experiment during punja season (Oct—Feb) in cultivators' fields in Kuttanad area, Alleppey, Kerala, under the Operational Research Project, studied the influence of herbicides on sheath blight and sheath rot control. The average disease scores of sheath blight and sheath rot are given in the table.

Average scores of sheath blight and sheath rot with different herbicides. Kerala, India.

Treatment	Sheath blight score (0-9)	Sheath rot score (0-9)
2,4-D spray at 1 kg a.i./ha	2.30	2.40
2,4-D at 1 kg mixed with 50 kg urea/ha applied to soil	3.35	3.15
Weedon (18%), 5 kg mixed with 50 kg urea/ha applied to soil	2.81	2.93
Benthiocarb (Saturn) granules at 2 kg a.i./ha applied to soil	3.15	2.75
Foliar application of benthiocarb at 2 kg a.i./ha	1.50	1.98
Hand weeding (control)	3.20	2.65

Symptoms of ufra disease of deepwater rice in Bangladesh

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Three symptom types are proposed for ufra (caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev) as it occurs under Bangladesh field conditions. The

Results indicate that spraying the foliage with benthiocarb (Saturn) reduced sheath blight and sheath rot.

Weeding is a problem for rice cultivation in Kuttanad. Because of the high labor cost involved in mechanical weed control, most farmers use chemical weed control. The information obtained through the present trial indicates that benthiocarb (Saturn) has an additional advantage of controlling sheath blight and sheath rot. These diseases are severe in this locality. ■

symptoms are based on the extent of panicle emergence (see figure). In ufra 1, the panicle fails to emerge; in ufra 2 the panicle exhibits partial emergence; and in ufra 3, the panicle emerges properly, but the grain remains unfilled. The categories *thor* ufra and *pucca* ufra by Butler correspond approximately to ufra 1 and ufra 3, respectively, although ufra 1 includes all panicles that fail to emerge, whether or not they also exhibit the spiral distortion characteristic of severe attack. The newly proposed

The symptoms of ufra (left to right): ufra 1, ufra 2, and ufra 3. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Dacca, Bangladesh.

symptom type, ufra 2, is intermediate between ufra 1 and ufra 3, but appears to be distinct. The proportion of panicles in a defined area classified as ufra 2 has been found useful as a disease index. ■

Components of yield loss from ufra

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Ufra (caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev) sometimes occurs in well-defined patches within a field in southern Bangladesh. At harvest the patches are often visible from a distance because stems bearing healthy panicles lodge whereas diseased stems, supporting empty heads, remain erect. There is a distinct gradient in disease intensity across a single field.

A field of this type, about 6.5 km west of Chandina in Comilla District, was selected in November 1978. Crop-cuts of 4 m² were made in different parts of the field: 3 where disease intensity was highest, 3 where it was moderate, and 3 where it was lowest.